

Landscape of risk: Integrated analysis of cyclist crash hotspots and emergency medical service coverage

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Abstract: *Cycling is among the most under-explored transport modes, which does not reflect its importance, especially in meeting the daily mobility needs of a large part of the world's population. One of the most important aspects of research is the safety of cycling, since cyclists are among the most vulnerable road users. This paper studies the temporal variability of bicycle crashes, defining bicycle crash hotspots and their accessibility by emergency medical service vehicles using the Czech Republic as an example. There is a significant concentration of bicycle crashes during specific parts of the year. We identified the main concentrations of cyclist crashes on the Czech road network using the Kernel density estimation+ method. Hotspots based on collective risk are mainly concentrated in urban areas but also rural regions. Although bicycle crash hotspots are generally accessible by emergency medical services, coverage is inadequate in some locations. Poorly accessible hotspots are particularly common in mountain and foothill regions, which are frequent destinations for cyclists seeking adrenaline and scenery.*

Keywords: *bicycle crash, cycling, spatial analysis, Hotspots, emergency medical service*

Introduction

Paradoxically, cycling is among the least explored transport modes, not only in geography but also in general, even though it is a common form of daily mobility for hundreds of millions to billions of people around the world. Moreover, cycling is also a popular discipline in professional sport and leisure for large segments of the population (Götschi et al. 2015, Bačík, Klobučník 2017). The increased interest in cycling research from a spatial perspective can be observed in roughly the last fifteen years. The main areas of current academic research include the study of cycling travel behaviour, social and cultural aspects, environmental contexts, economic impacts, and safety of cycling (Fishman 2015, Nikolaeva et al. 2019, Heinen, Buehler 2019, etc.). Although there are no exact statistics on the number of bicycles, global estimates indicate approximately 1 billion (Rodrigue 2020). However, there are significant regional differences in the global importance of cycling. In China alone, the number of bicycles is estimated at around 450 million units. Among European countries, the Netherlands is one of the leaders; here, the number of bicycles exceeds the total population (about 1.3 bicycles per capita). The key point is that bicycles are growing in popularity worldwide in response to the need for sustainable transport, reducing emissions, and promoting healthy lifestyles. The recent increase in the importance of cycling has also been linked to the development of bike-sharing concepts that promote using a bicycle as a healthy transport mode, particularly in urban areas (O'Brien et al. 2014). The bicycle gained importance especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, as it offered an affordable option for individual mobility over short distances in times of Covid restrictions, as well as a convenient transport mode to keep their users physically fit (Nguyen, Pojani 2022).

However, due to the increasing number of cyclists, conflicts with other road users are increasing. In the European Union, the number of cycling fatalities has long been around 2,000 per year, which is roughly 10% of all road fatalities. Interestingly, however, despite the safety measures introduced (safer infrastructure, helmet wearing, awareness campaigns, etc.), the number of bicycle crashes has not decreased in the long term (European Commission 2023). An extensive study on the number of bicycle crashes and the risk factors involved in seven European cities (Branion-Calles et al. 2020) shows, among other things, significant spatial differences in the number of bicycle crashes, which may be caused by several factors of both objective (differences in infrastructure, traffic education, overall traffic situation, etc.) and subjective nature (selecting the observed sample of respondents, individuals' driving style, etc.). The study also notes that many cycling crashes are not officially recorded due to minimal or no consequences. Cyclists, along with pedestrians and motorcyclists, are among the most vulnerable road users. Recent academic research has therefore increasingly focused on the risks of cycling (Loidl et al. 2016, Yang et al. 2021, Myhrmann and Mabit 2023) and ways to improve cyclist safety in road traffic (DiGioia et al. 2017, Pedroso et al. 2016, McLaughlin, Glang 2010). As cycling is associated with the concept of sustainable mobility in many cities and regions, the topic of increasing cyclist safety in road traffic has particular social relevance and perspective (Pucher, Buehler 2017). Cyclist safety and vulnerability in road traffic are the subject of many scientific disciplines. Since bicycle crashes take place in specific temporal and spatial conditions, this issue is also the subject of geographical approaches. These approaches focus on the detection and analysis of crash locations (Lee, Abdel-Aty 2017), the factors underlying cycling location riskiness (Lovelace et al. 2016), and the complex factors of cyclists' traffic behaviour (Heinen, Buehler 2019, Bi et al. 2023). The geographers' interest in cycling research has been longstanding (e.g. Aultman-Hall et al. 1997, Jones 2005), but only the recent availability of new spatial data with precise crash locations has made this area of geographical research very appealing with direct implications for practice.

The article focuses on the spatial and temporal analysis of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic. We use an innovative and original approach to comprehensively assess the riskiness of road network sections for cycling in the whole country. For the analysis, we use precisely localized data from bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic provided by the Police of the Czech Republic from 2016-2022. The secondary objectives of the study are to analyse the temporal variability of cyclist crashes (i); to identify cyclist crash hotspots (ii); and to analyse the coverage of crash locations by emergency medical service (iii). This approach is useful not only for understanding the spatiotemporal aspects of bicycle crash rates but also for a more comprehensive assessment on the appropriateness of the emergency service call station location relative to bicycle crash locations. The Czech Republic is one of the European countries with an above-average number of cycling fatalities, together with Romania, Belgium, Poland, Hungary, and Germany. The number of cycling fatalities in the Czech Republic in 2018-2020 was equal to 5.0 fatalities per million inhabitants, while the EU27 average was 4.4 fatalities (European Commission 2023).

The structure of the article is as follows. The introductory section is followed by a theoretical background of the issue studied. The main attention is paid to the discussion of the current state of knowledge in the field of research on bicycle transport and its safety. In the following section, data and research methods are presented. The analytical section is based on the objectives stated above. It analyses the temporal variability of cyclist crashes, identifies key hotspots of concentration of cyclist crashes and assesses the accessibility of crash locations for emergency medical service vehicles. The final section then provides a synthesis of the issues addressed and recommendations for further research.

Theoretical background

Cycling is an extremely popular form of daily mobility. Its significance is worldwide, as the bicycle is widely used in all parts of the world. However, there are significant spatial differences in the use of cycling. It has traditionally been associated with meeting the mobility needs of people in emerging economies (Adsule, Kadali 2024). This usually concerns countries in the Global South, where non-motorised transport modes play a relatively significant role in national transport systems (Brussel, Zuidgeest 2012). However, cycling plays an important role in developed economies as well, especially as part of sustainable mobility plans for cities and regions (Volker, Handy 2021). Based on a study of cycling in 17 countries on six continents, Goel et al. (2022) identify the key factors in cycling use. Among the most important are the level of cycling infrastructure, the distance and purpose of the trips, users' demographic and gender characteristics, and levels of urbanization.

Some authors note that bicycle transport has received marginal attention, even though its global importance is undeniable (see discussion in Agarwal et al. 2020, O'Reilly et al. 2024). Academic interest in cyclists and cycling has increased in roughly the last 15 years. The main reason for this increase is the wider societal acceptance of cycling as a common transport mode, with positive effects on the environment and physical health (e.g. Börjesson, Eliasson 2012, Lu et al. 2018). Other reasons include the increasing number of cyclists in traffic, the growing media attention towards traffic crashes, the activity of organisations promoting cycling, the improvement of cycling infrastructure, and legislative changes that have enabled improved cycling safety (obligation to wear a helmet, increased visibility of cyclists, improved education of cyclists and motorists, etc.). A promising area of research on cycling is its importance in sustainable mobility concepts. Growing mobility increases demands on transport infrastructure, including the associated negative environmental effects. The negative effects of increased transport demand are more pronounced in the long term, especially in urban areas, where traffic problems (exhalation, congestion, parking, etc.) accumulate. Promoting cycling thus becomes an effective tool to reduce car traffic, especially in urban areas (Gössling 2013). Recently, there has also been a rapid development in bike-sharing. The advantages of bike-sharing are short distance transport, environmental benefits, synergies with other transport modes, easy accessibility especially in urban areas, etc. (Eren, Uz 2020, Chen et al. 2020).

A specific area of research is the cycling crash rate, including the identification of key factors determining cyclist safety in road traffic. The results of several previous studies show that cyclist crashes are influenced by a wide range of underlying factors (Salmon et al. 2022). The most important include the transport infrastructure quality, traffic regulations, road user behaviour, weather conditions, visibility, cyclists' driving style, the vehicles' technical condition, and the way cyclists share roads with other transport modes (Chou et al. 2024). The interplay of these factors forms the external framework of cyclist road safety and crash rates. There are often issues with the behavioural aspects of road users (Schepers et al. 2014). These are particularly evident in collisions between cyclists and cars. These crashes are most frequently caused by excessive speed, negligence, lack of attention to driving, and aggressive behaviour, which can, however, be exhibited by both car drivers and cyclists. The most important geographical factors influencing bicycle crashes include the terrain, the presence of cycle paths and preferred bicycle lanes, the intensity of road traffic on a given section, weather conditions, and the area's attractiveness in terms of tourism (e.g. Chen 2015, Kim, Kim 2015, Lovelace et al. 2016, Prati et al. 2017, Wang et al. 2019, Costa et al. 2025). Identifying the key factors causing bicycle crashes is particularly important regarding planning measures to improve cyclist safety.

As mentioned above, cyclists are vulnerable road users. This is mainly because they have little or no protection during a collision. The most common types of cycling-related injuries

include head injuries, fractures of the upper and lower limbs, spinal injuries, etc. Life-threatening conditions include injuries to internal organs, especially the heart and lungs. Massive bleeding is a very common complication with these injuries (Beck et al. 2016). In the event of a crash, the rapid accessibility of adequate emergency medical service (EMS) is therefore crucial and has a major impact on post-accident safety for cyclists. In addition, it can play a key role in reducing the risk of bicycle crashes and injuries. Using the example of spatial analysis of motorcyclist crashes, Kraft et al. (2023) proved a positive relationship between the amount of time it takes for an emergency vehicle to reach a specific crash location and the mortality rate of those involved. Therefore, the time accessibility of EMS is a crucial attribute for the provision of post-accident care. In this case, the location of the crash plays a significant role, as the distance from the EMS dispatch station and availability of suitable road infrastructure in the area are decisive factors in ensuring timely medical care. However, a relatively high number of bicycle crashes happen in complicated and difficult-to-access terrain (Li et al. 2022). These specifics impair the accessibility of crash locations and the transport of patients to medical care, which in turn negatively affects their mortality. Geographical approaches to this issue should not only identify bicycle crash/risk locations but also study the coverage of crash locations by the time accessibility of EMS vehicles. Therefore, this study aims to address the research gap.

Data and methods

We use a combination of different data types for the analysis, primarily data on bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic from 1 January 2016 to 31 December 2022. The data were provided by the Police of the Czech Republic. The database contains records of all road crash reported to the Police in the given period. Only crashes involving cyclists as road users were filtered from this primary database. In total, there were 19,351 crashes involving cyclists in the period. For research purposes, only crashes in which the participants were injured were analysed further, i.e. crashes involving cyclists who were not injured were eliminated. This condition was met by 16,922 cycling crashes. Due to the nature of the KDE+ method, bicycle crashes that occurred directly at intersections were also eliminated. The applied KDE+ method is not intended to analyse accidents occurring at intersections (see Bíl et al. 2016). Therefore, all bicycle crashes within 50 metres of the nearest junction were excluded from the analysis. The resulting set of bicycle crashes analysed amounted to 15,961 crashes. Each crash record contains the exact GPS location of the crash, time data (time and date of crash), cause of crash, weather conditions, number and nature of injuries, and many other characteristics. These data were further supplemented by traffic characteristics (traffic volume) obtained from the database of average daily road traffic volumes provided by the Directorate of Highways and Motorways of the Czech Republic.

Through these data, significant concentrations of bicycle crashes (hotspots) on the Czech road network could be identified. Hotspots were identified using the KDE+ method, which is an extension of the common Kernel Density Estimation method (KDE+ 2020). The identified clusters are always the result of KDE, however, KDE+ makes it possible to objectively determine which clusters are statistically significant and to further sort such clusters according to their importance. A key indicator of each individual hotspot's importance is the collective risk indicator, which indicates the number of crashes per length of road section analysed. This method has been successfully applied to identify dangerous areas of road infrastructure (Bíl et al. 2013, Favilli et al. 2018, Kraft et al. 2022). The advantage of this method is that standard clustering methods (e.g. KDE, clumping method, K-function, or nearest neighbour method) work with planar (Euclidean) space and are therefore not suitable to identify clusters in a linear

arrangement (i.e., on a transport network). KDE+ places a kernel function (Epanechnikov kernel) into each point representing a given incident in each section and, in case of multiple incidents, the kernels are added. Local density function maxima represent hotspots. The higher the maximum, the more significant the hotspot. However, it is not possible to determine whether the difference between different hotspots is statistically significant. To determine the significance level, a Monte Carlo method is used, where points are repeatedly generated in each section according to a random uniform distribution and a kernel density estimate is determined for them. The significance level is then determined as the mean value of the function over the interval bounded by the length of the segment. If the kernel estimate of the incident density is above the calculated significance level in any part of the segment, the hotspot is identified as statistically significant.

Data on the time accessibility of bicycle hotspots from EMS stations were obtained through the time accessibility model from ArcGIS Pro 3.3. The exact location of individual EMS stations was taken from each individual region's coverage plan. In total, we analysed 327 EMS dispatch stations. Time accessibility was determined using the Network Analyst extension in ArcGIS Pro. The individual sections connecting the origin (EMS dispatch base) and destination (the centre of the surveyed road section) were assigned average speeds (according to the legislative standard CSN 73 6100-2). The time-accessibility model was further calibrated to the emergency vehicles' real travel speeds based on the findings of previous studies (Dolejš et al. 2020). The time required to reach the destination was then calculated for each section. Using this sub-procedure, we defined each individual crash location's accessibility, which significantly influences the possibility of rescuing injured persons.

Spatial and temporal analysis of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic

Temporal analysis of bicycle crashes

Bicycle crashes show specific temporalities rather than being evenly distributed throughout the year. The temporality of bicycle crashes is strongly influenced by the overall nature of traffic, weather conditions, average temperatures, hours of sunshine, and other factors (Chaney and Kim 2014). These factors also influence the pattern of bicycle crashes during the study period.

Fig. 1. Temporal distribution of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic, 2016-2022

Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

Crash temporality follows a very similar pattern across years (fig. 1), characterised by a minimal number of crashes during the winter months, a rapid increase in spring, a maximum in summer, and a relatively rapid decrease in autumn. The favourable conditions in the summer

months are ideal for cycling and the number of bicycle users is likely to increase. During this period, bicycles are arguably used not only for regular commuting trips but also for recreational purposes. In terms of crashes, the summer months are the riskiest period. However, a relatively high number of crashes has been recorded during other parts of the year as well. In terms of days of the week, Friday, Saturday, and Sunday are among the riskiest days, but the differences between the days are not significant. Bicycles are used mainly as a leisure activity during weekends. A similar crash temporality can be observed, for example, in crashes involving motorcyclists, which are also strongly influenced by their seasonal use as a transport mode primarily intended for leisure (Kraft et al. 2022).

Fig. 2. Temporal concentration of bicycle crashes according to month and hours in the Czech Republic, 2016-2022

Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

On the other hand, specific temporal crash concentrations can be identified in the cyclist crash rate. Fig. 2 shows the temporal concentration of crashes by month and hour during the day. A darker colour indicates a more pronounced concentration at a specific hour within a month, while a lighter colour shows a relatively even distribution. Crashes occurred almost year-round during the study period, however, the summer months are characterised by a concentration of crashes in the late afternoon and evening hours. This is mainly related to the lengthening of the days and the hours of sunshine in the summer months. However, crashes are mainly concentrated in the spring and autumn months between 3 pm and 5 pm. To some extent, this confirms the results of previous studies (such as Beck et al. 2016, Dash et al. 2022), but e.g. Myhrmann and Mabit (2023) concluded, using the example of a bicycle crash in Copenhagen, that the morning rush hour (7-8 am) is riskier. The differences may be caused by the fact that while the study analyses crash patterns in an urban environment, our study focuses on crashes throughout the whole country. The concentration of bicyclist crashes in the afternoon during the spring and fall months may be related to the overall traffic increase during the afternoon rush hours when more crashes occur (Griswold et al. 2018). However, for cyclists and their visibility, the glare of the setting sun on car drivers tends to be problematic during this period and can lead to cyclists being overlooked by car drivers (Mitra 2014). In this respect, cycling exhibits very specific temporal crash patterns compared to other transport modes.

Spatial Analysis of Bicycle Crashes

Bicycle crashes always take place in specific spatial conditions. It is therefore extremely important to identify the crash hotspots in terms of cycling safety. A routine visualisation of all analysed crashes reveals some regularities in the spatial organisation of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic (fig. 3). The crashes are concentrated in large urban environments, where individual risk factors for bicycle crashes (high population density, high traffic volume, and frequent sharing of lanes by cyclists and cars) are traditionally cumulative (see also Kraft and Tonev 2025). The concentration of crashes is evident in the largest Czech cities (Prague, Brno, Ostrava). Major intersections and traffic junctions are also among the areas with a high concentration of bicycle crashes. Again, the volume of road traffic is a risk factor here, generating conflicts between cycling and car traffic. A greater concentration of crashes can therefore be observed on main roads and in the hinterland of large cities. The Prague hinterland is an ideal example, as it often becomes a crash site for cyclists who seek to escape the city buzz but are threatened by the relatively intense car traffic in suburban areas (similarly e.g. Wang et al. 2019). A high crash concentration can be observed in attractive Czech tourist regions. These are typically popular cycle paths along rivers (Vltava, Elbe), mountain and foothill areas (the Giant Mountains, the Beskids, the Bohemian Forest), or attractive tourist regions with flat terrain and a lot of bicycles use for leisure purposes (South Bohemian region). Although this visualisation is useful for capturing the general patterns of bicycle crashes' spatial organisation of, it cannot be used to identify risky sections and individual hotspots. Below, we therefore focus mainly on identifying the hotspots using the KDE+ method.

Here, risk hotspots are expressed as crash concentration points on the road network using the KDE+ method. The analysis identified 431 statistically significant hot spots in the Czech Republic (fig. 4). They are concentrated in the eastern part of the Czech Republic (Moravia, Silesia), where the most important hotspots are also located. The eastern part of the Czech Republic is one of the regions where cycling is used the most for regular daily commuting trips (Kraft, Prener 2014). The most significant bicycle crash hotspots are expressed by collective risk (parameter *Str_Dense2*), which indicates statistically significant clusters of bicycle crashes on relatively short road sections. In general, the KDE+ method analyses clusters of crash concentrations relative to the existing road network. Surprisingly, the majority happen

outside urbanized areas (Lovelace et al. 2016). This indicates that although bicycle crashes happen more in cities, the most dangerous sections of the road network for cyclists are slightly more prevalent in rural regions (tab. 1). This indicates complications in transporting the people involved to hospitals since EMS are concentrated in urban regions.

Fig. 3. Bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic, 2016-2022
Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

Fig. 4. Bicycle crash hotspots in the Czech Republic between 2016 and 2022
Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

Tab. 1. *The most significant bicycle crash hotspots in the Czech Republic, 2016- 2022*

	All bicycle crashes	Bicycle crashes hotspots
Urban	6,380	171
Suburban	3,701	73
Rural	5,880	187
Σ	15,961	431

Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), Ouředníček et al. (2013), own calculations

Although in general, there is a higher number of hotspots in rural regions, the most important hotspots are predominantly located in urban environments. Of the top ten hotspots in the Czech Republic, nine are in urban areas (tab. 2). In general, the most significant hotspots are found on roads with high traffic volumes, usually without separate bicycle lanes. Urban hotspots are also often located in areas with rail traffic (rail, tram) where specific traffic rules result in collisions with cyclists. These factors in turn mean a high risk for cycling safety (Dozza, Werneke 2014). These specific hotspots should provide the basis for city and regional policies to increase cyclist safety and its overall promotion (see e.g. Ding et al. 2021, Short, Caulfield 2014, and others). Although there are more hotspots in suburban areas in terms of quantity, tab. 2 shows only the most significant hotspots in terms of collective risk. This means that there are more hotspots in suburban areas, but the most significant hotspots in terms of collective risk are mainly in urban areas.

Tab. 2. *The most important crash hotspots of cyclist in the Czech Republic, 2016-2022*

Rank	Locality (municipality)	Description	Collective risk	Length	Environment	Number of crashes
1	Kolín	route 12557 near roundabout	6.2	106.3	Urban	5
2	Prague	Štefánik bridge	6.0	111.0	Urban	5
3	Pardubice	route 324 near Pavel Wonka bridge	5.0	159.0	Urban	5
4	Staré Město	route 55 over Baťa channel	4.2	190.0	Urban	6
5	Prague	Na Slupi street,	4.2	55.0	Urban	4
6	Valašské Meziříčí	route 03561, Hřbitovní street, near railroad crossing	4.2	199.4	Urban	5
7	Opava	route 46, near railroad underpass	4.1	77.4	Urban	3
8	Prague	Smetanovo nábřeží	4.1	56.0	Urban	2
9	Karviná	17. listopadu street, near hospital	4.0	149.0	Urban	4
10	Ostravice	route 56, near the bridge over the Ostravice river	4.0	86.0	Rural	3

Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), Ouředníček et al. (2013), own calculations

Time Accessibility of Crash Hotspots from the Nearest EMS

The time accessibility of crash locations and their hotspots is another crucial factor in cycling safety. The timely arrival of emergency vehicles and the provision of medical care have a significant impact on the surviving cyclists' mortality rate. In terms of the accessibility of primary health care provision, the first minutes tend to be particularly crucial. Over time

the chances of survival decrease significantly (see e.g. Kraft et al. 2023). The above-mentioned set of 431 hotspots in the Czech Republic was analysed. Fig. 5 demonstrates that the distribution of emergency vehicle dispatch stations in the Czech Republic is relatively satisfactory, as a substantial part of the hotspots are accessible in a relatively very short time from the nearest EMS dispatch station. This is supported, among other things, by the fact that the most important bicycle crash hotspots are located mainly in urban environments. Cities have very frequent EMS stations and are equipped with good transport infrastructure that ensures relatively good accessibility to health care (Cittadini et al. 2024). On the other hand, due to the high traffic volume, especially in large cities, traffic congestion appears, often causing slower passage for ambulance vehicles and thus poorer accessibility of crash locations.

Fig. 5. Time accessibility of hotspots of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic, 2016-2022
Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

A more detailed demonstration of individual hotspot's accessibility for EMS vehicles is also provided by classifying hotspots into individual accessibility zones (tab. 3). As mentioned above, the provision of timely assistance through EMS is one of the crucial aspects of post-accident care for injured participants. Although most hotspots are accessible relatively quickly for EMS vehicles, there are also hotspots which are problematic. Hotspots where it takes 20 minutes or more for a EMS vehicle to arrive may be the most problematic ones. There is generally a rapidly increasing mortality rate for crash survivors in this category (see e.g. Silva and Padeiro 2020 or Li et al. 2022). 121 hotspots meet this condition; the smaller ones are generally concentrated in areas attractive to tourists for cycling. Typically, these are mountain and foothill areas (Giant Mountains, Jizera Mountains) or remote locations on lower-class roads, which affects their poor time accessibility. They are concentrated specifically in the "inner peripheries" of the Czech Republic. These are areas on the borders of self-governing administrative units of the Czech Republic with an accumulation of many negative socio-economic phenomena (see also Pileček et al. 2013). These areas are very popular for cyclists because of their remoteness and lower traffic intensity, providing a relaxing experience. However, in the event of a crash, these areas exhibit very poor time accessibility for EMS vehicles and thus potential problems in securing timely medical care.

Tab. 3. Time accessibility of hotspots of bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic, 2016- 2022

Time accessibility	Number of hotspots	Average collective risk
Less than 10 minutes	163	1.17
10 – 19 minutes	147	1.23
20 – 29 minutes	99	1.28
30 – 39 minutes	19	1.19
40 and more minutes	3	1.20

Source: Police of the Czech Republic (2024), own calculations

Discussion

The topic of cycling safety has become key in cycling studies in recent years. The easier availability of spatial data on bicycle crashes enables a more detailed and sophisticated crash analysis. Such analysis is extremely important for subsequent recommendations to eliminate bicycle crashes and further guide transport policy (Salmon et al. 2022). Spatial approaches should therefore aim to study the spatiotemporal variability of bicycle crashes and identify and analyse risky cycling locations (Loo, Tsui 2010). GIS integration plays an important role in this process, allowing not only the visualization of these elements but also their advanced spatial analysis.

This paper analyses the spatiotemporal aspects of bicycle crashes. It shows that crashes in the Czech Republic happen more often in the summer months when cycling is often used as a leisure activity. However, the afternoon hours in the spring and autumn months (March, April, and October), when many crashes occur, are the riskiest. This is due to the increased road traffic in the afternoon combined with an early sunset during these hours, leading to glare for drivers and thus making it easier to miss cyclists in traffic. Time changes (the transition between CET and DST) may also play a role here since the days become shorter due to the one-hour time shift backward, especially during winter. These results should be supported by a future detailed analysis of the people involved in crashes and the individual underlying factors (similarly Loidl et al. 2016). The study is focused on the collective risk; this is a limitation of this research. The exposure-adjusted risk could be more precise, however, this is beyond the scope of the current analysis.

Bicycle crashes are heavily concentrated in urban environments where various risk factors intersect. Urban hotspots are also often located in areas with rail traffic where specific traffic rules result in collisions with cyclists. Although quantitatively more crashes take place in urban environments (cf. Dash et al. 2022), more hotspot crashes were identified by the KDE+ method in rural areas outside urbanized areas. These areas are often sought out for leisure activities by residents.

Time accessibility to crash sites is one of the less studied factors in bicycle crashes and mortality rates. Even though crash hotspots are primarily concentrated in rural areas, their accessibility from the nearest EMS dispatch station is relatively very good in the Czech Republic. The coverage of crash locations is quite satisfactory, but there are still blank spots where crash hotspot accessibility is problematic. These are usually very remote mountain areas where mountain cyclists often crash. Although it is possible to deliver the patient from these locations to primary medical care, for example by helicopter, the conditions (visibility, weather conditions, etc.) are not always suitable for helicopter operation. An ambulance vehicle is therefore the only option which is always safe.

Nevertheless, there are some limitations to the research conducted. These include the fact that not all crashes are recorded. We studied bicycle crashes investigated by the Police of the Czech Republic, but many bicycle crashes may not be recorded, which is especially true for crashes without injuries. The accessibility model also provides an ideal state of time accessibility, i.e. a situation where a crash is reported, and an EMS vehicle is immediately dispatched. In practice, however, a situation may arise where the ambulance is not present at the call station and

is, for example, at a previously reported incident. In such a case, the second nearest vehicle is called, etc. Thus, to refine these models, the average accessibility times from real situations according to the GPS records of individual vehicles should ideally be used. However, current computational methods cannot yet handle such large databases. The study is focused on the collective risk; this is a limitation of this research. The exposure-adjusted risk could be more precise, however this is beyond the scope of the current analysis.

Conclusions

This study demonstrated that bicycle crashes in the Czech Republic are spatially and temporally uneven, with the highest risk occurring in the afternoon hours of spring and autumn. The results also highlighted the significance of urban and rural crash hotspots and their relationship to both infrastructure and leisure cycling patterns. Despite generally good emergency accessibility, several remote areas remain problematic in terms of time to reach crash sites.

Overall, the integration of spatial and temporal analyses using GIS has proven to be an effective approach for understanding and mitigating bicycle crash risks. Future research should focus on exposure-based risk assessment and the use of real EMS response data to improve the accuracy of accessibility modelling.

From a practical perspective, the findings of this study can inform transport policy and urban planning in several ways. Identifying spatiotemporal crash patterns provides valuable input for prioritizing investments in cycling infrastructure, especially in areas with repeated crash hotspots. Traffic management strategies should consider lighting conditions and visibility issues during transitional periods of the day and year. Improving road design in urban areas with rail intersections and introducing targeted awareness campaigns during high-risk months could also reduce crash rates. In addition, enhancing the monitoring and recording of bicycle crashes, particularly minor and unreported ones, would strengthen the evidence base for data-driven safety measures. Future research should extend these findings by incorporating cyclist exposure data, behavioral aspects, and detailed environmental variables such as road surface conditions or weather patterns. Combining spatial modelling with real-time mobility and sensor data could further refine risk prediction and enable proactive interventions for safer cycling environments.

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